

Water-ForCE Project Web Page

Project Identification	
Project Full Title	Water Scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Document Identification	
Deliverable number	D7.2.1
Deliverable Title	Water-ForCE Project Web Page
Type of Deliverable	Website
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP7
Leading Partner	isardSAT

History of Changes		
Date	Version	Comments
16.04.2021	V1	
16.03.2022	V2	update after receiving first year review

Project Web Page

The project webpage is up and running since March 15th, 2021 at the following web address:

<https://waterforce.eu/>

The website includes among other items:

- An overall description of the project and its objectives, information sheets and other publicity material for the project which will be available for download.
- Publicity and information about Webinars and Workshops organised by Water-ForCE where discussion with stakeholders is engaged.
- Papers and presentations by the members of the consortium and other papers of interest. Presentations and a poster giving a project overview. Publicly available project working documents.
- Details of the project consortium with links to their sites as well as information about the different Working Groups.
- A method for contacting the project, a way of joining the project mailing list and information on how to contribute to the project and in particular to the roadmap.
- links to Water-ForCe social media:
 - twitter (@h2020WaterForCE)
 - LinkedIn (linkedin.com/company/Water-ForCE)
 - vimeo (https://vimeo.com/user161489764)

Following reviewers comments the project webpage was updated on March 16th, 2022. Among other the following updates have been implemented:

- In section 'the project' a description of the project objectives together with main outcomes is provided. This section also provides material to be downloaded: poster, slides and document providing summary of project objectives and main outcomes.
- In section 'documents' deliverables have been withdrawn, project publications and working documents are now available to download.
- Furthermore, section 'contact us' has been updated to reach stakeholders in a more friendly way.

